

Revocable Gateway-Centric Trust for Consumer Electronics Using Distributed Ledger Technology

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Abstract—Consumer electronics increasingly execute integrated sensing–communication–computing–control (ISCCC) loops locally, making trust, revocation, and audit at the moment of action the bottleneck. We propose an architecture that maintains action-time authorization on the household gateway while synchronizing cross-vendor trust state off-path through a permissioned trust registry. Devices do not write to the ledger; instead, the gateway periodically anchors succinct commitments (Merkle roots and policy/model digests). We implement a proof-of-concept registry on an IOTA DLT and evaluate three aspects. First, for off-path anchoring, we show that under microbursts of size-triggered commit batches the ledger time-to-confirmation remains narrow and milestone-dominated (median around 3.9–4.0 s and 95th percentile around 4.2 s at a ~ 10 s coordinator cadence), with no sensitivity to burst size. Second, for registry reaction, we observe that revocation reaction time scales predictably with the snapshot cadence plus a few seconds of confirmation and probing delay: tightening the snapshot period from 60 s to 15 s shifts the empirical reaction-time distributions as expected. Third, for partition tolerance, we show that across normal, impaired, offline, and recovery phases, local decision latency remains in the sub-millisecond range (with only a few milliseconds of conservative extra latency when snapshots age) and anchoring resumes within the same 1–5 s confirmation envelope once connectivity returns. Overall, the results confirm that action-time decisions remain within tens-of-milliseconds budgets, while trust synchronization is predictable and tunable. In this setting, snapshot cadences of approximately 10–15 s for “hot” items (keys and ownership) and at least 60 s for “warm/cold” items (recalls and model checkpoints) provide a practical balance between revocation speed and polling cost. The open-source implementation is available at: <https://github.com/farhanajaved/PDL-Trust>.

Index Terms—Consumer electronics, trustworthiness, permissioned DLT, IOTA.

I. INTRODUCTION

Consumer electronic (CE) are best understood as a fabric of user-facing devices that autonomously coordinate multi-step tasks across integrated sensing, communication, computing, and control (ISCCC). Driven by rapid advances in Internet of Things (IoTs), Artificial Intelligence (AI), and wireless communication systems, these devices now enable real-time data collection, on-device processing, and intelligent decision-making for smart homes, wearables, and health monitoring systems. In practice, this is edge-time orchestration: locks, cameras, thermostats, wearables, appliances, and in-vehicle systems exchange signed state and intent so that control actions (unlock, adjust, admit, disarm, dispatch) meet strict latency, reliability, privacy, and energy requirements while delivering personalized,

context-aware services. As local networks (Thread/Wi-Fi, with optional cellular backhaul) and device capabilities advance, functions that once depended on cloud round-trips shift to edge computing on local controllers. The bottleneck therefore moves to trust at the moment of action: can the requester be proven authentic, in a known-good software state, and authorized for this capability under the current household policy? These issues of identification, authentication, authorization, and ongoing trust management define next-generation consumer electronics and underpin network reliability in ISCCC [1].

Much of the enabling infrastructure is standardized. Commissioning is shifting from ad hoc pairing to attested onboarding with common semantics for cross-vendor local control. In radio, 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) Release 17 introduces NR-RedCap to reduce modem complexity and energy consumption, bringing wearables, sensors, and video endpoints into 5G [2]. In parallel, Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ACE-OAuth) enables short-lived, audience-bound authorization, and RATS conveys attestation evidence; microcontrollers can present tokens and integrity proofs verifiable by a local gateway at decision time. European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI) sets a baseline for consumer IoT security. Together, these elements support AI-driven, context-aware authorization within the local control loop.

A canonical scenario illustrates both promise and gaps. In a Release 17/18 home, a *RedCap* wearable signals presence, a door camera provides a second factor, and the gateway queries an attested indoor sensor; the decision is made locally within tens of milliseconds using ACE-OAuth for per-capability authorization (“unlock”) and RATS freshness to gate higher-risk actions. With 3GPP “personal IoT”, household-anchored identities and policies become first-class [3]. Release 19 Ambient-IoT formalizes ultra-low-power tags and reader roles, such as curbside lockers or smartphones acting as readers, again requiring authorized readers and attributable events. While others remains the baseline, correctness now depends on fresh identity, authenticated approvals, and cross-vendor revocation propagation, precisely where today’s consumer electronics are least uniform [4].

Challenges become clear at the moment of action. First, identity is a lifecycle (provisioning, onboarding, service binding, repair, resale, end-of-support) and supersession is fragile. Second, authentication is often treated as a single event. Third,

authorization remains too coarse for the level of risk. Fourth, integrity and update recency rarely influence authorization. Finally, revocation and recall lack verifiable, cross-brand propagation. At the same time, households need audit trails (“who approved what, when, under which policy”) without centralizing raw audio, video, or presence data. For this reason, addressing these issues is central to resource allocation in ISCCC. Compute, airtime, and battery must be used for the decisions that matter, while keeping communication overhead predictable.

Intelligence in the loop adds a complementary dimension but does not change the fundamental bottleneck. Models that drive perception, prediction, and policy must be trustworthy; their versions and datasets should be identifiable, training and inference contexts attestable, and adaptations such as on-device or federated updates auditable without exposing raw data. Rather than shipping models or context off-premises, we treat model and policy artifacts as first-class items in the trust state: they are represented as cryptographic digests and governed by the same revocation and supersession machinery as keys and ownership. These constraints reveal clear opportunities: move trust-state synchronization *off* the fast path by using a permissioned trust registry as an append-only memory for revocations, ownership transfers, policy/version commits, and succinct anchors to model artifacts or decision logs. With control loops kept local, authentication uses ACE-OAuth and gates on Remote Attestation Procedures (RATS) freshness; devices consult the registry only to determine whether identities, policies, or referenced models have been superseded, with verifiable provenance. This arrangement enables real-time responsiveness, improves cross-vendor interoperability, reduces WAN dependence, and creates headroom in energy and airtime budgets. More broadly, it supports context-aware, AI-assisted authorization and auditable model adaptation without exposing raw data, aligning integrated sensing, communication, computing, and control with trustworthy operation at consumer scale.

Household-scale ISCCC requires ordered, non-equivocating multi-vendor supersession (revocations, recalls, ownership transfers, policy/model checkpoints) under partial trust. Therefore, we instantiate a permissioned, replicated ledger as a governed, append-only trust registry and keep it strictly off the action path. The ledger provides (i) operator-independent non-equivocation and (ii) a globally ordered history with attributable writer roles and eviction, which a single-operator transparency log cannot guarantee under concurrent, cross-vendor updates. We identify a set of architectural design principles that, to the best of our knowledge, are not explicitly articulated in previous ETSI PDL-, SCITT-, or DLT-based trust management frameworks for this setting. This work makes the following contributions:

- First, we establish that ISCCC-class latency budgets require the ledger to be architecturally excluded from the action path, rather than merely hidden behind a cache. Based on this principle, we propose a gateway-centric trust architecture for consumer electronics in which authorization and integrity checks are performed locally under explicit freshness and integrity gates (ACE-OAuth, OSCORE/EDHOC, RATS/EAT, SUIT), while raw context

data never leaves the home. This design preserves the fast control loop within sub-tens-of-milliseconds budgets even when the ledger is temporarily unavailable and aligns with emerging CE security practices.

- Second, we enforce gateway-only write authority as a privacy and governance invariant. Accordingly, we instantiate a permissioned ledger-backed trust registry in which end devices never write directly to the ledger. Instead, the household gateway anchors succinct commitments (e.g., Merkle roots and policy/model digests) using rotating identifiers and jittered batching. We further formalize revocation reaction time as a function of snapshot cadence and ledger confirmation time, thereby treating the ledger as a tamper-evident *trust memory* rather than a runtime dependency. This provides an analytical bound that makes snapshot cadence a concrete deployment parameter for determining revocation responsiveness.
- Finally, we implement the architecture on an IOTA-based DLT setup and evaluate three aspects: off-path anchoring under microbursts, registry reaction time under different snapshot cadences, and partition tolerance. The results show that anchoring delay is primarily cadence-dominated and that revocations can be kept within tens of seconds, while local decision latency remains in the sub-millisecond range. We provide practical configuration defaults for “hot” (keys/ownership) and “warm/cold” (recalls/model checkpoints) trust items. The evaluation shows that the primary deployment levers are snapshot cadence and coordinator scheduling, rather than ledger throughput or consensus tuning.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews related work on CE trust, standards-based authorization and attestation, and DLT-backed registries. Section III presents the CE setting, threat assumptions, trust model, and main architectural components. Section IV reports results on off-path anchoring, registry reaction time, and partition tolerance, and distills deployment guidance. Table I summarizes the principal notation used throughout the paper.

TABLE I
SUMMARY OF KEY NOTATIONS USED THROUGHOUT THE PAPER.

Symbol	Description
t, d, c	Current time, device, and capability
τ, ε	Authorization token and attestation evidence
P, M, R	Active policy, model artifact, and trust registry snapshot
$\Delta_{\text{att}}, \Delta_{\text{snap}}$	Attestation and snapshot freshness bounds
$L_{\text{action}}, \theta_c$	Action-time latency budget and per-capability risk threshold
ρ	Soft risk score
$T_{\text{rev}}, T_{\text{TTC}}$	Revocation reaction time and ledger time-to-confirmation
ε_{net}	Network/polling jitter term

II. RELATED WORK

Recent efforts in CE and IoTs security have addressed trust, authorization, and accountability across device ecosystems. Surveys such as [5] have outlined how trust and reputation systems enable collaboration among heterogeneous IoT devices [6], [7],

while emphasizing that dynamic, cross-vendor trust propagation remains unsolved. At the device level, the IETF Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ACE-OAuth) framework [8] adapts OAuth 2.0 for constrained nodes, supporting token-based authorization. Complementing this, the RATS architecture [9] defines a formal model for verifying device integrity via signed evidence, and the Software Updates for the Internet of Things (SUIT) specification [10] ensures firmware authenticity and freshness through manifest-based verification. Together, these standards establish a foundation for trustworthy operation in constrained consumer devices, but they do not address multi-vendor synchronization or verifiable lifecycle events.

Beyond device-centric mechanisms, distributed trust infrastructures have been explored to ensure auditability and non-equivocation across domains. The ETSI Permissioned Distributed Ledger (PDL) framework [11] and the IETF SCITT architecture [12] both propose using permissioned ledgers to store verifiable statements about digital artifacts, such as credentials, ownership, and recalls. These architectures provide immutability and provenance but are not designed for real-time decision loops in household or edge contexts. Complementary research formalizes blockchain-based trust and access in IoT. In [13], the authors propose a blockchain-based trust management method in which mobile edge nodes compute sensor trust and anchor results on-chain. The authors in [14] present a blockchain-based trust model for IoT supply chains, emphasizing integrity and low-latency sharing. Recent surveys categorize blockchain-enabled trust for IoT and Industrial IoT, highlighting open issues in cross-domain synchronization and lifecycle integration [15], [16]. On the intelligent edge, [17] uses federated learning to compute device reputation and stores scores on blockchain for tamper resistance, while [18] combines edge anomaly detection, federated training, and trust-aware access control to adapt permissions in real time. These advances demonstrate how AI and DLT improve trust and auditability, yet most treat attestation, authorization, and audit as separate layers or assume a single-domain trust boundary.

In contrast to previous efforts, our work *unifies* device integrity (RATS/EAT), secure lifecycle management (SUIT), and authorization (ACE-OAuth) within a gateway-centric trust architecture backed by a governed, permissioned ledger that serves as a verifiable trust registry. More specifically, ETSI PDL and SCITT provide important reference mechanisms for governed records, signed statements, and verifiable registration, but they do not explicitly address how ledger-backed trust should be architecturally excluded from real-time decision loops in latency-sensitive edge or household settings, nor do they provide quantitative guidance linking registry configuration to revocation timeliness. Similarly, existing DLT-IoT trust frameworks [13], [14], [17] typically couple trust evaluation or trust-state publication with blockchain-backed workflows and assess the resulting latency, storage, or throughput costs, rather than formulating ledger off-path operation as an explicit design principle and formalizing the corresponding configuration trade-offs. Instead of recording raw context, the gateway periodically anchors concise cryptographic commitments, such as Merkle roots of policies, models, and event digests, to a

permissioned DLT aligned with the ETSI PDL governance model. This approach enables attributable governance, deterministic supersession, and non-equivocation across vendors while preserving user privacy, as devices never write directly to the ledger. Empirical results on an IOTA DLT validate the analytical reaction-time bound. During network partitions, a *Trust Cache* enables deterministic local decisions with deny-or-escalate semantics, followed by idempotent reconciliation once connectivity resumes, thus maintaining continuity and partition tolerance. Together, these features deliver holistic ISCCC trust management for consumer electronics, advancing beyond prior work in both scope and verifiable performance.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a CE environment comprising sensing endpoints (e.g., cameras, motion sensors, wearables), actuators (locks, thermostats, appliances), and a local controller that coordinates ISCCC pipelines over Thread/Wi-Fi, with optional cellular backhaul (NR-RedCap today; with Rel-19 Ambient-IoT extending reader/tag roles). Control loops close locally, sensors provide context, short-range radios exchange signed state, the controller performs on-device inference and evaluates policy and actuators commit or reject actions within a bounded latency budget L_{action} on the order of tens of milliseconds. Raw audio, video, and presence data remain local and only compact trust signals and digests leave the home domain when required for safety, maintenance, or compliance, consistent with baseline consumer IoT guidance [19], [20].

The ledger contains only cryptographic commitments and status, periodic Merkle roots of local decision logs, policy/model digests, ownership/credential status codes, and timestamps. Device/user content (audio, video, presence, sensor traces) remains on-premises. Gateways do not publish stable per-device identifiers, and writer events are role-scoped. To limit linkability, anchors are batched and jittered. Low-criticality events may be delay-anchored, and per-household anchor identifiers are rotated. Gateways consume signed “as-of” snapshots with height and verify timeliness locally. Audit queries operate over digests and require local pre-image possession. This follows data-minimization practices for consumer IoT and our design, which keeps action-time decisions local while synchronizing only succinct trust state off-path.

Each device d has an identity established during manufacturing and onboarding, and is associated with policies. Onboarding uses attested commissioning (e.g., Matter Device Attestation Certificates chained to PAAs/PAIs with per-fabric operational credentials). At the moment of action, the controller verifies short-lived, audience-bound authorization tokens τ and recent attestation evidence ε , and decides on per-capability requests (e.g., `door.unlock`) under the active policy P . Evidence freshness is enforced by $\Delta_{\text{att}} \leq \Delta_{\text{max}}$; authorization tokens include scope, audience, and expiry to constrain replay, with profiles suitable for constrained endpoints (ACE-OAuth with OSCORE transport security and EDHOC bootstrapping). Decisions must satisfy L_{action} without reliance on wide-area round trips [8], [21], [22].

Trust state evolves over time. We model a passive, permissioned trust registry R that maintains an append-only record of

(i) ownership bindings and supersession events, (ii) credential and key status (revocation, suspension, reason, issuer), (iii) recall and quarantine notices at firmware/model-lineage granularity, (iv) policy *and model* version checkpoints represented as cryptographic digests, and (v) audit commitments as succinct hashes of local decision logs. The controller ingests signed snapshots or proofs from R asynchronously and enforces a staleness bound Δ_{snap} ; action-time decisions consult the local cache, not R , preserving the real-time budget. These artifacts align with attestation and update primitives (RATS/EAT, SUIT) and can carry transparency receipts when available [9], [10], [12], [23].

A. Threat Model

Our threat model requires that revocations, recalls, and ownership supersession issued by multiple vendors be applied in a non-equivocating, globally ordered manner and remain auditable beyond any single operator. A permissioned, replicated ledger with role-scoped writers satisfies these properties by design: (P1) non-equivocation (no unilateral rollback or conflicting views), (P2) total order of updates for deterministic supersession, (P3) attributable governance (onboarding/eviction of writers, validator rotation), and (P4) verifiable snapshots consumable by gateways. In contrast, a single-operator or mirrored transparency log provides efficient inclusion proofs but, in the presence of faults, does not provide governed total order or eviction without introducing an external consensus that effectively recreates the ledger. Therefore, we use the ledger solely as a trust memory. Gateways ingest signed *as-of* snapshots and enforce freshness bounds locally and raw content, context, and actuation never traverse the ledger. This design aligns with our results, where anchoring time to confirmation is milestone-dominated and load-insensitive in our setup. This confirms that off-path synchronization governs staleness, while the action-time budget remains local and within the tens-of-milliseconds envelope.

Adversaries may exploit stale or superseded trust states (e.g., keys that should be revoked, ownership changes not propagated, recalls not applied) or attempt to replay authorization under changed policy. We assume devices support secure boot and attestation roots; time is loosely synchronized within δ ; the local controller is within the trusted computing base; and writers to R are permissioned and attributable. Where cellular connectivity is available, SIM/eSIM security and provisioning can root identities and keys (IoT SAFE; GSMA SGP.31/32 for constrained, large-scale fleet management). The objective is to prevent unsafe actuation under outdated assumptions while maintaining latency, privacy, and energy efficiency [24]–[26]. Beyond stale or superseded trust state, we also consider additional adversarial behaviors at the registry and governance layer. A *malicious or colluding writer* is constrained by role-scoped, attributable writer keys with governed eviction (P3, G-2), while non-equivocation (P1) and total order (P2) limit the ability of a colluding minority to introduce conflicting committed updates. *Delayed or censored revocation publication* is mitigated at the gateway by invariant I1: if the snapshot age exceeds Δ_{snap} , the gateway fails closed, so suppression is

expected to degrade availability rather than safety. *Snapshot manipulation* is addressed by signed “as-of” snapshots with ledger height; the gateway verifies signature and height monotonicity locally, rejecting rollback or stale replay. *Governance failures* are mitigated through periodic validator rotation (G-1), threshold-based finality, and the dispute mechanism (G-5). Full compromise of the consortium governance quorum remains out of scope and is treated as a trust-base failure.

Operations are defined over these artifacts. *Commission* binds a device to the household and records an ownership event in R . *Actuate* verifies τ and ε , evaluates P , and commits the action if constraints are met. *UpdatePolicy* changes P and anchors a new digest. *TransferOwnership*, *RevokeKey*, and *RecallModel* append corresponding records to R . Controllers periodically ingest updates from R ; upon detecting supersession of an identity, policy, credential, or referenced model, subsequent actions are evaluated under the updated trust state without incurring WAN dependency at decision time. This model preserves local autonomy and treats trust synchronization as an off-path, rate-limited activity. Formally, the system ensures authenticity and integrity at action time, provides fine-grained authorization consistent with the current P , enforces bounded propagation of revocations and ownership changes (service-level objective T_{rev}), and enables auditability through commitments that do not expose raw data. The trust registry serves as an architectural role; its instantiation uses a permissioned, append-only ledger with role-scoped writers and verifiable snapshots. In what follows, we describe an architectural system and trust model.

B. Trust Model

We instantiate action-time authorization with minimal notation: t (time), d (device), c (capability), τ (token), ε (attestation), P (policy), M (model), R (registry snapshot). Freshness bounds are Δ_{att} (attestation) and Δ_{snap} (registry) and action-time budget L_{action} . The construction follows constrained-device authorization and transport (ACE-OAuth over OSCORE with EDHOC) and remote attestation/update freshness (RATS/EAT, SUIT), with cross-vendor state synchronized via a permissioned transparency/registry [8]–[10], [12], [21]–[23], [27], [28]. The trust model in this subsection is intentionally specified at the architectural level: it defines invariants, hard gates, and soft risk scoring as policy and deployment knobs.

To make the safety posture explicit, the gateway enforces five always-on invariants: (I1) *Freshness* if $t - t_{\text{snap}} > \Delta_{\text{snap}}$ the gateway denies or escalates; (I2) *Monotonicity Trust Cache* updates only tighten effective rights and indexer/relayer faults never loosen policy; (I3) *Time bound* dangerous actions require $|\Delta t| \leq \delta$ and fresh evidence ($a_{\text{att}} \leq \Delta_{\text{att}}$, $\exp(\tau) > t$); (I4) *Diversity* when multiple signals or approvals are used, they should come from distinct trust domains (vendor, sensor class, network path) to reduce correlated failure; (I5) *Anchor hygiene* only content-addressed digests and Merkle roots are committed off-path to the registry, and raw content never leaves the home.

Hard gates: Evaluate only if all hold: (H1) $\text{valid}(\tau) \wedge \text{bindsToSession}(\tau) \wedge \exp(\tau) > t$; (H2) $t - t_{\text{att}} \leq \Delta_{\text{att}}$; (H3) $t - t_{\text{snap}} \leq \Delta_{\text{snap}}$; (H4) $\neg \text{revoked}_R(d) \wedge \neg \text{quarantined}_R(d)$; (H5) $\text{digest}_R(P) = \text{digest}_{\text{local}}(P)$ and $\text{digest}_R(M) =$

digest_{local}(M). If any (H1)–(H5) fails, deny (fail-safe). Additionally, the gateway enforces the trusted time bound $|\Delta t| \leq \delta$; violations are treated as immediate deny. H1 is enforced with ACE-OAuth tokens bound to the authenticated OSCORE/EDHOC session; H2 uses RATS/EAT evidence age and SUIT freshness; H3–H5 rely on signed “as-of” snapshots from a permissioned registry [8]–[10], [12], [21]–[23], [27].

Soft risk: If (H1)–(H5) pass, score residual risk $\rho \in [0, 1]$ from freshness and context. Using ages $a_{att} = t - t_{att}$, $a_{snap} = t - t_{snap}$, $a_{model} = t - t_{model}$, anomaly $z \in [0, 1]$, and uncertainty $u \in [0, 1]$:

$$\rho(d, c, t) = \sigma\left(\beta_0 + \alpha_a \frac{a_{att}}{\lambda_a} + \alpha_r \frac{a_{snap}}{\lambda_r} + \alpha_m \frac{a_{model}}{\lambda_m} + \beta_z z + \beta_u u\right), \quad \sigma(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}. \quad (1)$$

$\lambda_{\{\cdot\}}$ are freshness scales (half-lives) and $(\alpha_a, \alpha_r, \alpha_m, \beta_z, \beta_u)$ are calibrated weights; β_0 is a bias (with $\alpha_a, \alpha_r, \alpha_m, \beta_z, \beta_u \geq 0$ and $\lambda_a, \lambda_r, \lambda_m > 0$). For example, for a safety-critical action such as `door.unlock`, a deployment would typically assign greater weights to attestation freshness and snapshot freshness (α_a, α_r) than to model age (α_m), so that stale device state or stale trust snapshots dominate the risk score. For lower-risk actions such as lighting control, the policy can tolerate larger freshness windows and use smaller α_a, α_r with a less stringent threshold θ_c .

Decision: Permit \iff (H1–H5) \wedge ($|\Delta t| \leq \delta$) \wedge $\rho \leq \theta_c$, with capability-specific θ_c (e.g., $\theta_{\text{unlock}} < \theta_{\text{lights}}$). If any invariant is violated (e.g., $t - t_{snap} > \Delta_{snap}$ or $|\Delta t| > \delta$), the gateway fails closed (deny) or escalates according to the capability class (e.g., require additional confirmation or out-of-band approval). This realizes continuous, risk-adaptive authorization while keeping the fast path local and anchoring strictly off-path, consistent with CE data-minimization practice. In our proof-of-concept evaluation (Algorithm 1), we use a simplified instantiation of ρ in which snapshot age a_{snap} is the dominant variable. The gateway maps cache age into three discrete operating tiers (fresh, cautious, and degraded), chosen to approximate representative regions of the underlying sigmoid-based policy, while the remaining inputs are fixed or abstracted. Calibration of the full weight vector from operational data is left for future work.

Service objectives: $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{decide}}] \leq L_{\text{action}}$ and $\Pr\{\text{Permit after revoke at } t_0, t > t_0 + T_{\text{rev}}\} \leq \varepsilon_{\text{rev}}$. T_{rev} is engineered via the snapshot cadence Δ_{snap} , ledger time-to-confirmation T_{TTC} , and immediate local invalidation on revocation proofs, as captured by the bound below. The revocation objective is realised by choosing Δ_{snap} and coordinator cadence so that the observed T_{rev} distributions stay within the target window, keeping sensitive content local while only status/digests leave the home [27], [28].

Revocation reaction time (bounds):

$$T_{\text{rev}} \leq \Delta_{\text{snap}} + T_{\text{TTC}} + \varepsilon_{\text{net}} \quad (2)$$

where T_{TTC} is the ledger time-to-confirmation and ε_{net} lumps indexer polling granularity and network jitter. This is a strict worst-case bound (miss an entire snapshot period, then confirm,

plus propagation slack). Under random phase, the *expected* reaction time is smaller and follows the derivation in (5).

Queueing check: Because anchoring confirms in periodic milestones, it acts as a shaper for the registry and does not back-pressure action-time authorization. Even if anchoring lags, decisions use the local *Trust Cache* and remain bounded by L_{action} ; if cache age exceeds Δ_{snap} , the gateway fails closed (deny) or escalates per capability class (I1–I2).

C. Architectural key components

The ETSI ISG PDL favors vertical *profiles*: role-checked, minimal subsets that define optional fields, encodings, and access rules to ensure interoperability and conformance [28]. CE in ISCCC requires the same discipline: identities (IEEE 802.1AR DevID, W3C DIDs, Matter) and evidence (ACE-OAuth, RATS/EAT, SUIT) vary widely; without a common binding, gateways cannot deterministically verify cross-brand recalls, key revocations, or ownership transfers. We propose a PDL profile for CE that (i) standardizes the required record types, (ii) assigns role-specific write permissions, and (iii) specifies transport and timeliness guarantees for gateway ingestion. Real-time grant/deny decisions remain at the household gateway (attestation and fine-grained policy); the ledger serves as a controlled, tamper-resistant trust memory. The profile separates an *append-only anchoring layer* from an *Ethereum Virtual Machine (EVM) compatible contract layer* that hosts rolegated registries (ownership, credential/key status, recalls, policy digests, audit commitments). Gateways use gas-sponsored meta-transactions through a *Ledger Adapter/Relayer* and consume verifiable snapshots from an *Indexer/Chronicle*, rather than full nodes or token custody. In the following section, we explain the most important components and the workflow. The architecture of the permissioned DLT profile for CE trust management is shown in Fig. 1. Ten components are described below:

(i) *Household Gateway (decision point):* Locus of run-time authorization, evaluating capability and context-aware policy and driving actuation. It moves authority to the edge (Matter/Thread/Wi-Fi; optional cellular signalling, e.g., Red-Cap), satisfying autonomy and latency/availability constraints by avoiding cloud roundtrips.

(ii) *Policy Engine:* It implements capability- and context-aware authorization (e.g., `door.unlock` with temporal/presence constraints). Binds device trust to action-level rights, aligns with consumer capability models (e.g., matter clusters), and references standardised terms where available.

(iii) *Identity Manager:* It maintains device and household credentials; supports manufacturer identities (IEEE 802.1AR DevID, platform roots) and household-scoped decentralized identifiers (DIDs) and verifiable credentials (VCs) (e.g., IOTA Identity). Commissioning takes place via authenticated on-boarding (e.g., Device Provisioning Protocol (DPP), Matter attestation). Ownership transfers/supersession is captured as VC updates/revocations and mirrored on-ledger to prevent ghost ownership.

(iv) *Evidence Verifier:* It validates short-lived, audience-bound, capability-scoped CBOR Web Token (CWT) / CBOR Object Signing and Encryption (COSE) tokens (ACE-OAuth)

Fig. 1. Permissioned-DLT profile for CE trust management. Red-outlined blocks and blue arrows denote proposed components and interfaces.

and appraises integrity via RATS/EAT and Software Updates for the Internet of Things (SUIT), coupling authentication and integrity with authorisation to exclude outdated or compromised software.

(v) *Trust Cache*: It holds freshness-checked, signed snapshots of the on-ledger state (ownership bindings, key status, recalls/quarantines, policy versions) with explicit time-to-live (TTL) values that enable deterministic local decisions under partition and fast convergence on reconnection.

(vi) *PDL Consortium Plane*: An IOTA Smart Contracts (ISC) chain (EVM runtime) plus a permissioned Tangle for append-only anchoring realizes a governed ledger without a public token economy. Chronicle permanode and index/query services provide persistent, signed views; governance defines validator membership, writer roles, and deterministic conflict resolution.

(vii) *Governance profile* Validator membership is permissioned with threshold finality; operators are onboarded via consortium policy and rotated on schedule (G-1). Writers are role-scoped (vendor, operator) and onboarded with attestable role keys; misbehavior or key compromise triggers on-ledger eviction and key roll (G-2). Keys (validators, writers, relayer) follow periodic rotation with immediate revocation on compromise, and rotations are themselves anchored (G-3). Consortium-sponsored meta-transactions enforce per-writer rate limits and per-epoch sponsorship budgets; on limit breach, relayer back-

pressures and the gateway queues idempotent writes (G-4). Conflicts and disputes are logged as first-class records and resolved by governed total order (no unilateral rollback); appeals use co-signed dispute entries (G-5). Indexer/Chronicle advertise freshness SLOs (e.g., minutes for entry systems) and expose signed *as-of* snapshots with height, enabling gateways to verify timeliness locally (G-6).

(viii) *On-ledger trust registries (ISC/EVM)*: Five role-checked contracts define canonical records for the decision point: (i) ownership/supersession bindings; (ii) credential/key status (revocation/suspension with issuer, scope, reason); (iii) recall/quarantine notifications (model or firmware lineage granularity, optional co-signers); (iv) policy/version checkpoints (cryptographic digests of active policies); and (v) audit commitments (periodic Merkle roots of decision logs). EVM provides sophisticated tools and role-based access control (RBAC); Tangle anchoring ensures a tamper-proof history.

(ix) *Ledger Adapter*: It computes commitments over local decision logs, batches household revocations, ownership supersessions, and policy checkpoints, and transmits via consortium-sponsored meta-transactions (no token custody). Remote Procedure Call (RPC)/query exposes signed, indexed views with freshness service level objectives (SLOs) (e.g., minutes for entry systems) for timely cross-vendor propagation.

(x) *Southbound and northbound interfaces*: In southbound,

Fig. 2. Gateway decision and anchoring workflow.

S1 commissioning, S2 runtime tokens and attestation over restricted transports (Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) / Object Security for Constrained RESTful Environments (OSCORE) / Ephemeral Diffie–Hellman Over COSE (EDHOC)) or Transport Layer Security (TLS) / Datagram TLS (DTLS), S3 batched gateway writes to the relay and S4 anchoring from ISC registries to the permissioned Tangle are performed. In northbound, N1 actuation commands to CE devices, N2 signed snapshots from Chronicle/Indexer to the *Trust Cache*. Role-scoped ports PR-1 (vendor recalls), GR-1 (governance updates), RL-1 (relay ingress), IX-1 (indexer egress) bound ingress/egress. Sensitive data remains on-premise; only identifiers, status, and cryptographic commitments are transferred to the ledger, in accordance with data minimisation policies.

D. Workflow

Figure 2 illustrates the sequence of the proposed workflow¹. At runtime, the gateway issues a unique *decision_id* and challenge, collects capability-scoped approvals within a bounded window, validates signatures, expiry, and *decision_id*-bound

nonces, binds tokens to the session if available, and removes duplicates using $\langle \text{approver_id}, \text{decision_id}, \text{nonce} \rangle$. Cached on-ledger registrations are then checked using a signed “as-of” snapshot with height to confirm current ownership, non-revocation, applicable recalls/quarantines, and that the *gateway-selected* policy/version is in force (request hints must match and never downgrade).

The gateway executes or denies requests and writes a minimal log binding the decision to the policy/version identifier, cache “as-of” metadata, and *decision_id*-salted approval hashes under a monotonic timebase, while the raw content remains on-premises. Each decision record is compact, containing a policy or version identifier, cache “as-of” metadata, and salted approval hashes, so short-term storage requirements are modest. Once a batch has been successfully anchored and the corresponding Merkle root confirmed on-ledger, the raw entries may be pruned from local storage, retaining only the anchored root and minimal batch metadata as a compact audit reference. A configurable retention window (e.g., 7–30 days) allows operators to balance local storage footprint against on-premises audit depth; entries beyond the window are garbage collected, while their anchored roots on the ledger preserve tamper-evident verifiability.

On a jittered cadence, a Merkle root is computed over new logs, and both the root and policy digest are anchored to the registries using an idempotent *anchor_id*. During backhaul loss, the gateway operates on cached trust with stricter local policy (for example, deny or require additional confirmation under staleness) and queues anchors and idempotent writes for later commit. The runtime behavior of the gateway under this workflow is summarized in Algorithm 1, which makes the trust-cache update loop, snapshot refresh, and asynchronous anchoring explicit. Recommended defaults (consistent with our evaluation) are $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \approx 10\text{--}15$ s for “hot” items (keys/ownership) and $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \geq 60$ s for “warm/cold” items (model checkpoints, recalls), maintaining action-time latency while bounding revocation staleness.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATIONS

We evaluate the proposed system model, where the household gateway batches local *GatewayDecision* records and asynchronously anchors a compact commitment (Merkle root and policy/model digest) as a *LedgerCommit*. The *GatewayDecision* arrivals are generated synthetically as short microbursts, with burst size and intra-burst spacing configured to be in the same range as burst characteristics reported for the IoT Traffic Analytics IPFIX dataset². Each *LedgerCommit* aggregates 20 *GatewayDecision* entries into a single ≈ 2.5 KB JSON payload. The *ledger confirmation time* (TTC) is measured from the moment the *LedgerCommit* is posted to the Hornet REST API (`/api/core/v2/blocks`) until the block is referenced by a milestone (referencedByMilestoneIndex). The simulation environment and gateway client configuration used for all experiments are summarized in Table II.

¹Open-source implementation: <https://github.com/farhanajaved/PDL-Trust>

²<https://iotanalytics.unsw.edu.au/iotipfixrecords.html>

Algorithm 1 Gateway trust-cache and partition-tolerance

Require: snapshot cadence Δ_{snap} , decision rate R_{dec} , batch size B

- 1: $t_{\text{snap}} \leftarrow \text{now}$; $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow \emptyset$; initialize durable queue \mathcal{Q}
- 2: **Loop 1: Action-Time Decision Processing**
- 3: **for each** decision event **do**
- 4: $A_{\text{cache}} \leftarrow \text{now} - t_{\text{snap}}$
- 5: **if** $A_{\text{cache}} \leq \Delta_{\text{snap}}$ **then**
- 6: $(p, \delta) \leftarrow (0.95, 0 \text{ ms})$
- 7: **else if** $A_{\text{cache}} \leq 2\Delta_{\text{snap}}$ **then**
- 8: $(p, \delta) \leftarrow (0.50, \mathcal{U}(2, 4) \text{ ms})$
- 9: **else**
- 10: $(p, \delta) \leftarrow (0.10, 0 \text{ ms})$
- 11: **end if**
- 12: wait δ ; draw $\text{permit} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p)$
- 13: log t_{decide} and permit ; append decision to \mathcal{B}
- 14: **if** $|\mathcal{B}| = B$ **then**
- 15: build LedgerCommit payload from \mathcal{B} ; enqueue into \mathcal{Q} ; $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow \emptyset$
- 16: **end if**
- 17: **end for**
- 18: **Loop 2: Trust-Cache Snapshot Refresh**
- 19: **loop** every Δ_{snap} seconds
- 20: attempt heartbeat to registry/node
- 21: **if** request succeeds **then**
- 22: $t_{\text{snap}} \leftarrow \text{now}$ {Reset cache age}
- 23: **end if**
- 24: **end loop**
- 25: **Loop 3: Asynchronous Ledger Anchoring and Retry**
- 26: **loop**
- 27: dequeue next payload from \mathcal{Q}
- 28: **if** no payload available **then**
- 29: wait briefly; **continue**
- 30: **end if**
- 31: POST payload to ledger
- 32: **if** send fails **then**
- 33: requeue payload and **continue**
- 34: **end if**
- 35: **end loop**

TABLE II
SIMULATION ENVIRONMENT & WORKLOAD

Host OS	Linux (Ubuntu 22.04 LTS)
CPU	12th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-1265U, 10 cores, max frequency 4.8 GHz
Memory	31 GiB DDR4
Docker Containers	Hornet Node 1: CPU 0.59%, 583.9 MiB Hornet Node 2: CPU 3.13%, 581.6 MiB INX Coordinator Traefik (proxy) Monitoring / explorer services deployed
PDL Setup	Hornet v2.0.2 Base token: SandCoin (SAND) Milestone interval: default ≈ 10 s
Gateway Client	Python 3.10; <code>requests.Session</code> ; poll interval 0.25 s Warm-up: 3 milestones; node health checked via <code>/api/core/v2/info</code>

To reflect realistic CE scenes (door+motion+lights+camera), the gateway emits *microbursts*: small groups of commits sent back-to-back (tens of milliseconds apart), followed by an idle period of approximately 1 s. We test four load tiers, $L_t \in \{10, 30, 50, 100\}$ (commits per run). Polling resolution for confirmation is 0.25 s; both the time-to-next/milestone at send time and the observed milestone interval are logged for analysis. This anchoring occurs *off* the action-time path; authorization decisions use the local *Trust Cache* (H1–H5), consistent with keeping L_{action} within the tens-of-milliseconds budget.

The experiments isolate the off-path cost of trust synchronization: time-to-confirmation tracks the coordinator cadence and shows no evidence of queue-induced tails under our microburst workload, while action-time authorization remains local via the *Trust Cache*. These observations support the design choice of a replicated trust registry for governed order and non-equivocation, without introducing wide-area variability into the fast control loop.

A. Off-Path Anchoring under Microbursts (TTC)

We measure the ledger time-to-confirmation (TTC): the elapsed time from the HTTP POST of a LedgerCommit to Hornet’s `/api/core/v2/blocks` until the block is referenced by a milestone (`referencedByMilestoneIndex`). Each commit batches 20 GatewayDecision entries into a ≈ 2.5 KB JSON payload (Merkle root + policy/model digest). Decision arrivals are synthetically bursty, with b and δ chosen so that burst size and spacing fall in the same order of magnitude as the burst patterns reported in the IoT Traffic Analytics IPFIX traces; the on-chain payload remains synthetic (Merkle root and digests only).

Commits are issued as microbursts (burst size b , intra-burst gap $\delta \ll 1$ s), followed by ≈ 1 s idle. This mirrors correlated CE event chains (e.g., door, motion, light/camera) and keeps the offered rate well below node saturation. The average rate is:

$$\bar{\lambda} \approx \frac{b}{(b-1)\delta + 1 \text{ s}} \quad (3)$$

In our runs this evaluates to $\bar{\lambda} \approx 1$ commit/s, so TTC is governed primarily by milestone timing rather than client backlog. The 1 s idle also spreads bursts across different milestone phases; optional sub-second jitter can further decorrelate from the 10 s schedule.

We evaluate four run sizes $L_t \in \{10, 30, 50, 100\}$ and poll confirmation every 0.25 s (quantization error ≤ 0.25 s, negligible versus the few-second TTC). The coordinator uses the default ≈ 10 s milestone cadence. To verify the node is not back-pressured, we sample the durable queue once per second; it remained empty for the entire run (median = 0, P95 = 0, max = 0 batches) across all tiers, and no block exceeded $2 \times$ the milestone interval. Timing uses monotonic clocks and buffered I/O; the single-host client–node path contributes only sub-millisecond to few-millisecond RTT, far below the milestone cadence. Under these conditions, TTC is milestone-dominated and load-insensitive, as evidenced by the overlapping TTC distributions across L_t in Fig. 4 and Fig. 3. Using the observed median $T_{\text{TTC}} = 3.86$ s as a typical value, the *expected* reaction

Fig. 3. CDFs of TTC for burst anchoring with $L_t \in \{10, 30, 50, 100\}$.

time satisfies $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{rev}}] \approx \Delta_{\text{snap}}/2 + 3.86 \text{ s} + \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_{\text{net}}]$, so revocation effectiveness is governed by snapshot cadence plus commit time, not by the action-time control loop.

Fig. 4. Distribution of TTC under microbursts across load tiers.

Anchoring is intentionally *off the action path*: it provides tamper-resistant auditability and cross-vendor synchronization without back-pressuring local authorization. Across L_t , TTC distributions are nearly indistinguishable (Fig. 4, 3), with median $\approx 3.9\text{--}4.0 \text{ s}$, P95 $\approx 4.2 \text{ s}$, and P99 $\approx 4.26 \text{ s}$; no timeouts are observed and no commit exceeds $2\times$ the milestone interval (20 s). The visibly longer *lower tail* at $L_t=10$ is expected from a phase-sampling effect of the milestone cadence combined with small- N coverage: with only ten commits, microbursts do not fully cover the milestone cycle, so a few posts land just before a milestone and confirm quickly, adding probability mass at short TTC. As L_t increases (30–100), bursts span more phases of the $\sim 10 \text{ s}$ schedule and the distribution collapses into a narrow band around the cycle average, eliminating the apparent tail. Importantly, the upper tail is bounded (no samples beyond $\approx \text{P95} \sim 4.2 \text{ s}$ and none above $2\times$ the milestone interval), which rules out node backlog; the shape is cadence-dominated rather than queue-induced.

Since anchoring is asynchronous, these times do not affect L_{action} ; they bound the staleness of the auditable record and the pace of trust synchronization.

B. Registry Reaction Time and Snapshot Cadence

We define the *registry reaction time* T_{rev} as the elapsed time from an authorized write to the permissioned trust registry until the household gateway enforces the change via its signed *Trust Cache*. The gateway ingests verifiable snapshots from a registry on a fixed cadence $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \in \{15, 60\} \text{ s}$; action-time authorization remains local (H1–H5), with the ledger used solely for off-path synchronization. For each event we log the registry write time t_{write} , the ledger confirmation time t_{confirm} (first `referencedByMilestoneIndex`), the first snapshot that contains the change $t_{\text{cache_seen}}$, and the first denied action probe t_{deny} . Thus,

$$T_{\text{rev}} = (t_{\text{confirm}} - t_{\text{write}}) + (t_{\text{cache_seen}} - t_{\text{confirm}}) + \varepsilon_{\text{probe}} \quad (4)$$

The first difference represents the ledger time-to-confirmation T_{TTC} , while the second captures the wait until the next snapshot that includes the change. The term $\varepsilon_{\text{probe}}$ accounts for discretization from the action probe rate; with $f_{\text{probe}} = 2 \text{ Hz}$, we have $\varepsilon_{\text{probe}} \leq 0.5 \text{ s}$ and, under random phase, $\mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_{\text{probe}}] \approx 0.25 \text{ s}$. Taking expectations yields

$$\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{rev}}] \approx \frac{\Delta_{\text{snap}}}{2} + \mathbb{E}[T_{\text{TTC}}] + \mathbb{E}[\varepsilon_{\text{probe}}] \quad (5)$$

because writes arrive with an (approximately) uniform phase relative to the snapshot grid, while $\mathbb{E}[T_{\text{TTC}}]$ is a cadence-independent few seconds in our setup (Sec. IV-A).

T_{rev} bounds how quickly revocations, key rotations, recalls, or policy/model updates take effect *without* putting the ledger on the critical authorization path. It exposes a tunable freshness-overhead trade-off: smaller Δ_{snap} provides faster enforcement at higher polling/processing cost, while larger Δ_{snap} reduces cost at the price of a longer stale window.

For each cadence $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \in \{15, 60\} \text{ s}$ we generate three event families *RevokeKey*, *RecallModel*, and *TransferOwnership* with $N = 50$ events per family and per label (`normal/impaired`; labels only, no network shaping), totaling 300 events per cadence (600 overall). Confirmation is polled every 0.25 s

(quantization ≤ 0.25 s). The action probe rate is $f_{\text{probe}} = 2$ Hz. We warm up for ~ 3 milestones (≈ 30 s) and record the observed milestone interval, which remains near the default ~ 10 s. We use a fixed random seed (42) for reproducibility. The client and node are on the same host path (sub-ms to few-ms RTT), far below the milestone cadence.

The CDFs *translate* with Δ_{snap} (Fig. 6): with $\Delta_{\text{snap}} = 15$ s, mass concentrates around ≈ 10 – 20 s; with $\Delta_{\text{snap}} = 60$ s it spans ≈ 20 – 60 s. Box plots (Fig. 5) show medians near $\frac{1}{2}\Delta_{\text{snap}}$ plus a small, cadence-independent offset equal to the ledger confirmation time (a few seconds; cf. Sec. IV-A), and an additional vertical lift of at most 0.5 s attributable to probe discretization. No heavy tails or secondary modes appear beyond Δ_{snap} plus a few seconds, and distributions overlap across event families under the same cadence, indicating cadence-dominated (not event-specific) behavior.

Fig. 5. Box plots of T_{rev} grouped by Δ_{snap} .

Fig. 6. Registry reaction time T_{rev} under two snapshot cadences ($\Delta_{\text{snap}}=15$ s and 60 s).

These observations are consistent with (4)–(5) and confirm the architectural intent: (i) *trust synchronization dominates* post-revocation latency in this regime, with ledger variance secondary; and (ii) *local action-time decisions remain decoupled* from wide-area conditions and stay within the tens-of-milliseconds budget L_{action} by consulting freshness-bounded cache state (RATS/EAT, SUIT, and ACE-OAuth over OSCORE

with EDHOC underpin H1–H2 [8]–[10], [21], [22]). Practically, choose $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \approx 10$ – 15 s (or add event-driven push) for “hot” items (keys, ownership), and $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \geq 60$ s for “warm/cold” items (model checkpoints, recalls) to reduce polling cost.

Equation (2) provides the conservative design bound for revocation reaction time, while Equation (5) captures its expected central tendency under random phase. The experiments in this subsection instantiate these relations for $\Delta_{\text{snap}} \in \{15, 60\}$ s, Tightening the snapshot cadence shifts the T_{rev} distribution accordingly, confirming that revocation timeliness is governed primarily by snapshot cadence plus the few-second ledger confirmation delay, rather than by the action-time authorization path.

C. Partition-Tolerance Evaluation

We stress the gateway’s partition-tolerance with four connectivity phases *normal*, *impaired*, *offline* and *recovery* while keeping authorization on the local *Trust Cache* and anchoring commitments off-path as implemented in Algorithm 1. The gateway issues local decisions at a fixed rate and batches them into ≈ 2.5 KB *LedgerCommits* (batch size 5 in this run). We log (i) local decision latency t_{decide} , (ii) anchor TTC from POST to milestone reference, and (iii) cache-age evolution via periodic snapshot ticks ($\Delta_{\text{snap}} = 15$ s). Figures 7 and 8 summarize the results.

Fig. 7. Local decision latency t_{decide} by phase (log-scale y-axis).

These measurements directly test the two guarantees in the system model: (i) action-time decisions governed by (H1–H5) remain fast and local, limited by the freshness of a signed snapshot; and (ii) audit anchoring is asynchronous, so variability in ledger confirmation time does not affect authorization latency. Across phases, we expect t_{decide} to remain in the sub-millisecond range except during brief intervals when cache age exceeds Δ_{snap} (in which case the policy deliberately introduces a small additional delay of 2–4 ms). For anchoring, we expect TTC to be predominantly milestone-dominated (≈ 1 – 5 s with a ~ 10 s milestone cadence), largely insensitive to moderate

Fig. 8. Transaction time to confirmation (TTC) distribution across phases.

latency and loss, and to return to the same envelope once connectivity is restored.

Figure 7 confirms that the authorization fast path remains sub-millisecond in the *normal* and *impaired* phases. The few isolated outliers (e.g., a single ~ 13 ms sample in *normal*) are consistent with operating-system scheduling and I/O effects rather than with the decision logic, which adds no delay when the *Trust Cache* is fresh. In the *offline* phase and the initial part of *recovery*, cache age briefly exceeds Δ_{snap} and the caution tier injects the intended 2–4 ms wait, producing the modest vertical spread in the box plots; occasional 5–6 ms samples again appear as rare scheduling artefacts. Importantly, no heavy tail emerges and medians and 95th percentiles remain within a few milliseconds across all phases, indicating that action-time authorization is effectively decoupled from backhaul conditions.

Figure 8 shows that TTC is primarily milestone-dominated and insensitive to the connectivity phase. Whenever sends are possible, confirmations cluster in the 1–5 s band with no timeouts, consistent with the coordinator’s ~ 10 s cadence plus polling jitter. In the *recovery* phase, TTC distributions concentrate in the same band (median around 1 s; 95th percentile around 5 s): commits issued just before a milestone confirm almost immediately, while those just after wait for the next milestone. During *offline*, commits are queued and then confirm within this same envelope once connectivity resumes, demonstrating a bounded backlog and rapid catch-up within a small number of milestones. Snapshot ticks follow the expected pattern, with resets in *normal/impaired*, monotonic growth in *offline*, and rapid reset in *recovery*, confirming that cache age and anchoring behavior match the intended partition-tolerance design.

D. Discussion

Taken together, the experiments validate the architectural choice to keep the ledger strictly off the action path. Off-path anchoring shows a narrow, cadence-dominated time-to-confirmation envelope under realistic microburst patterns, so

the ledger functions as a shaped, append-only trust memory rather than a throughput bottleneck. Registry reaction times are primarily determined by the snapshot cadence and only secondarily by ledger confirmation jitter, which matches the analytical bounds derived from Δ_{snap} and T_{TTC} . The partition-tolerance results further show that authorization can remain a purely local operation: decision latency stays within sub-tens-of-milliseconds budgets across normal, impaired, offline, and recovery phases, with only a small policy-induced delay when operating on aged snapshots. In practical terms, the main configuration levers available to implementers are the snapshot cadence and coordinator schedule, rather than ledger throughput or consensus settings. This aligns with emerging guidance that positions permissioned ledgers as governed transparency and registry layers, while real-time decisions continue to execute at the edge.

A cloud-centric trust service offers simpler deployment and centralized administration, but if consulted at decision time it introduces an external trust dependency and WAN sensitivity on the action path, which conflicts with the local-autonomy and partition-tolerance goals of this architecture [29]. Transparency-log approaches (e.g., Certificate Transparency [30] and SCITT [12]) provide append-only evidence, receipts or inclusion proofs, and post hoc auditability, but they do not by themselves define the same governed multi-writer ordering or gateway-consumable trust-state snapshot model assumed here. Conventional revocation services such as OCSP [31] and CRL mechanisms [32] provide certificate-status information, but not cross-vendor lifecycle ordering, policy supersession, or the same form of auditable trust-state snapshots.

From the architectural trust model, the proposed design preserves safety because action-time permission is granted only when the freshness, revocation, and policy-consistency conditions captured by I1 and H1–H5 hold; otherwise, the gateway denies or escalates. Fault tolerance follows from keeping authorization strictly local and the ledger off the action path, so degraded connectivity affects trust-state freshness and availability, but not the local verification path itself. This is consistent with the revocation bound in (2) and with the partition-tolerance results above. From an energy perspective, the design concentrates ledger-specific overhead at the household gateway, since CE devices never write directly to the ledger and anchoring is amortized through batching; therefore, snapshot cadence remains the main deployment trade-off between responsiveness and overhead. Full hardware-based energy measurements are left for future work.

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We proposed a revocable, gateway-centric trust architecture for CE, where authorization and attestation remain on the household gateway, while cross-vendor lifecycle events are synchronized off the fast path through a permissioned trust registry. Our implementation and measurements confirm that this separation can be achieved with bounded and tunable delay. Although our proof of concept uses IOTA, the qualitative behavior is expected to generalize to other permissioned ledgers

because the dominant factor is the bounded confirmation/finality delay, rather than raw consensus throughput. For other DLTs, such as Hyperledger Fabric, this delay is determined mainly by the orderer block-cutting parameters, whereas in Hyperledger Besu IBFT/QBFT, it is determined mainly by the configured block period and validator consensus. Thus, changing the ledger primarily affects the confirmation constant, while the architectural conclusion remains the same: action-time decisions remain local, and revocation latency is determined by the snapshot cadence plus confirmation delay.

Future work will extend the evaluation to multi-gateway and comparative multi-ledger integration with the proposed trust plane and emerging ecosystems such as Matter and Ambient IoT to conduct end-to-end energy and cost assessments on hardware testbeds. Another direction is to refine risk scoring and quorum policies. using operational data from deployed systems, while preserving the core architectural principle.

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